

Complete quantum-inspired framework for computational fluid dynamics

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(Dated: August 13, 2023)

Computational fluid dynamics is both an active research field and a key tool for industrial applications. The central challenge is to simulate turbulent flows in complex geometries, a compute-power intensive task due to the large vector dimensions required by discretized meshes. Here, we propose a full-stack solver for incompressible fluids with memory and runtime scaling polylogarithmically in the mesh size. Our framework is based on matrix-product states, a powerful compressed representation of quantum states. It is complete in that it solves for flows around immersed objects of diverse geometries, with non-trivial boundary conditions, and can retrieve the solution directly from the compressed encoding, i.e. without ever passing through the expensive dense-vector representation. These developments provide a toolbox with potential for radically more efficient simulations of real-life fluid problems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Navier-Stokes equations are one of the biggest remaining open problems in classical physics [1], with closed-form solutions known only in restricted settings. This has given rise to the field of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), entirely devoted to numerical tools for simulations [2]. Most state-of-the-art methods rely on a problem-specific discretization of the spatial domain, a *mesh*. There, the velocity and pressure fields are represented by vectors whose dimension is given by the mesh size. However, the precision required to capture relevant dynamics often translates into prohibitively high dimensions. For instance, for an accurate description of turbulent flows, the ratio between the largest and the smallest length scale in the mesh must grow with the Reynolds number [3, 4]. The resulting mesh can then have sizes that render the problem intractable for standard methods. This is a manifestation in CFD of the infamous *curse of dimensionality*, and it constitutes the most serious limitation of standard mesh-based solvers in practice.

A similar limitation arises in simulations of quantum many-body systems, described by Hilbert spaces exponentially large in the number N of particles [5, 6]. There, sophisticated tensor-network techniques [7–9] have been developed to tackle the problem under the assumption of limited quantum entanglement, i.e. non-factorability of the state vector [10]. The best-known example is matrix-product states (MPSs) [11, 12], also known as tensor trains [13]. These represent exponentially-large vectors as a 1D array of N matrices whose maximal size (called *bond dimension*) depends on the amount of entanglement. Hence, low-entangled states can be exponentially compressed by MPSs. This explains the good performance shown by MPSs at simulating the dynamics of 1D quantum systems [5, 7–9]. Today, MPSs and their tensor-network extensions provide the most powerful framework

for simulating complex quantum dynamics [14, 15].

In view of this, explorations have been launched to apply MPSs to a variety of other high-dimensional problems [16–21]. In particular, it has recently been observed that turbulent fluids in simple geometries can also be described by MPSs of low non-factorability [22–24], remarkably. The rationale is that the energy cascade mechanism [3], whereby energy transfer takes place only between adjacent spatial scales, may play a similar role to local interactions in 1D quantum systems. This may open a new arena for CFD solvers. Nevertheless, for this to happen, compression efficiency should be combined with other basic features. The most crucial one is the versatility to describe immersed objects of diverse geometries, with non-trivial boundary conditions. Moreover, a practical solver should also allow for accessing the solution directly in the MPS encoding, without passing through the dense vector. Otherwise, potential speed-ups in solving the problem may be lost at evaluating the solution. It is an open question whether these requirements can be harmoniously met and, most importantly, if there are settings of practical relevance where this can be achieved with a moderate bond dimension.

Here, we answer these questions in the affirmative. We deliver a complete MPS-based framework for simulating incompressible fluids, with both memory and runtime scaling logarithmically in the mesh size and polynomially in the bond dimension. We achieve this via three major innovations: First, we develop *approximate MPS masks* that encode object shapes into MPSs of significantly lower bond dimension than the direct discretization of their boundary surfaces. Second, we introduce an efficient time-integration procedure incorporating the masks as native, built-in features. Our approach is based on finite-differences as in [22, 23], but it operates with open boundary conditions, as in [24], crucial to treat immersed objects without excessively large spatial domains.

Interestingly, our integrator embeds open boundary conditions directly into a matrix-product differential operator (differential MPO). Third, we develop *MPS solution oracles* for accessing the solution even when the mesh size is too big for dense-vector evaluations. The oracle can be queried in two main modes: *coarse-grained evaluation* and *pixel sampling*. The former automatically gives an averaged version of the field. The latter generates random points according to their relevance to a chosen property, such as vorticity or pressure, e.g..

We run numerical simulations with diverse geometries. First, for the paradigmatic flow around a cylinder, we successfully reproduce the well-known Kármán vortex street [25]. Additionally, we observe reasonably good agreement in the length and frequency of the vortices with available experimental data. Second, for flows around a square cylinder, we validate our solutions against those of the **Ansys Fluent** commercial solver, at different times and for Reynolds numbers up to $\text{Re} = 2230$, observing good qualitative agreement. Finally, we venture into more complex geometries: a collection of squares and even a real-life airfoil from the NACA data set. For the squares, we simulate long-time evolutions until vortices emerge. The agreement between the visual patterns observed with those of the commercial solver is remarkable. To our knowledge, this is the first MPS algorithm for fluid simulations validated to such extents. For the airfoil, we showcase the versatility of the MPS solution oracle. For instance, with a 19-bit MPS, we use pixel sampling to randomly explore the regions of highest vorticity around the wing, without evaluating a single component of the 2^{19} -dimensional vorticity vector field. These tools may be relevant for aero- and hydrodynamic design optimizations.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Incompressible Navier-Stokes equations

We wish to simulate the fluid dynamics arising from the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations (INSE)

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v} + \vec{f}, \quad (1a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0, \quad (1b)$$

where $\vec{v}(\vec{x}, t)$ is the velocity field, ρ is the fluid density, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and \vec{f} is the sum of the body forces acting on the fluid. Eqs. (1a) and (1b) follow from the momentum and mass conservation laws, respectively [4, 26, 27]. They can give rise to a variety of different flow regimes, ranging from laminar to fully turbulent flows. The type of flow regime is determined using the Reynolds number, $\text{Re} = \frac{UL}{\nu}$, where U and L are the characteristic velocity and length scale of the problem. Re is a dimensionless parameter that quantifies the ratio between the inertial forces ($\sim (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v}$) and dissipative

forces ($\sim \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v}$). At high Re , the nonlinear inertial term dominates and the flow is highly chaotic and turbulent. Instead, at low Re , the dissipative term dominates and the flow is stable and laminar.

B. Vector field encoding with matrix product states

Matrix product states (MPSs), also known as tensor trains, are a powerful, compact representation of high-dimensional tensors with a local structure. In particular, they provide a highly efficient ansatz to describe many-body quantum states with low entanglement [7–9]. Here, we introduce MPSs to encode real functions of two variables, such as the velocity field components $v_x(x, y)$ and $v_y(x, y)$, or the pressure field $p(x, y)$. We focus explicitly on the 2D case for simplicity, but all our construction can be straightforwardly extended to the 3D case.

We discretize functions over $N = N_x + N_y$ bits, giving rise to a 2^N -dimensional grid, or *mesh*. More concretely, we represent a continuous scalar function $v(x, y)$ with a vector of components $v_{i,j} := v(x_i, x_j)$, where the bit strings $\mathbf{i} := (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{N_x})$ and $\mathbf{j} := (j_1, j_2, \dots, j_{N_y})$ give the binary representation of integers between 1 and 2^{N_x} and 2^{N_y} , respectively. Then, in the MPS representation, each element $v_{i,j}$ is equal to the product of matrices

$$v_{i,j} = A_1^{(i_1)} A_2^{(i_2)} \dots A_{N_x}^{(i_{N_x})} B_1^{(j_1)} B_2^{(j_2)} \dots B_{N_y}^{(j_{N_y})}, \quad (2)$$

where the indices i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{N_x} and j_1, j_2, \dots, j_{N_y} are called *physical indices*. A pictorial representation of an MPS is given in Fig. 1c. The bond dimension χ of the MPS is defined as the maximum matrix dimension over all matrices in Eq. (2). In this work, we choose the particular encoding where the first N_x bits correspond to x -axis and the remaining N_y bits enumerate y -axis, as already performed in [21, 23]. However, other choices of encoding are possible [16, 28]. Importantly, the total number of parameters in all $2N$ matrices in Eq. (2) is at most $2N\chi^2$. Hence, in the particular case of χ constant, the MPS provides an exponentially compressed representation of the 2^N -dimensional vector. Moreover, for our simulations, instead of fixing all virtual dimensions at χ , the solver dynamically adapts the matrix dimension at each MPS site according to the amount of inter-scale correlations. This allows us to reduce the number of parameters well below the bound $2N\chi^2$ in practice.

In the MPS representation, the binary discretization of the domain dictates the notion of spatial scales. Namely, the first bit splits the domain in two halves, while the second bit splits each of the two halves into two more sub-halves and so on. Since the the bond dimension measures the amount of correlation between bits [7, 8], MPSs with small χ correspond to functions with limited correlations between scales. More precisely, MPSs with low bond dimension arise when long-range correlations are suppressed [8]. Following the intuition in [22], we then

FIG. 1. **Schematics of the framework.** **a.** Algorithmic pipeline of the solver, featuring the paradigmatic steady flow around a cylinder. The first step shows the flow initialization with constant velocity. The second step pictures the MPS mask application, which nullifies the velocity field inside the object (see Sec. III A). This produces an artificial field that is not divergence-free. To correct for this, in the third step, we project the field back onto the divergence-free manifold, defined by Eq. (1b). The fourth step performs the time integration over a small evolution time step, using an explicit Euler method. The last three steps are then iterated T times to get the final MPS field at time T (see Sec. III B). Finally, the fifth ingredient is the MPS solution oracle. The two boxes there represent the main operation modes of the oracle: coarse-grained evaluation and pixel sampling. **b.** Construction of the approximate MPS mask (for a 1D object for clarity). First, we consider a smooth function $q(x)$ (shown in light blue together with its absolute value shown in green) that vanishes on the boundary of the object. From $q(x)$, we construct the function $m(x) = 1 - e^{-\alpha(q(x)+|q(x)|)}$ (red solid). This approximates the object’s indicator function (black dashed) up to a small tunable error in α . Next, we apply the TT-cross algorithm to produce an MPS approximation to $m(x)$, requiring only a few queries of it. **c.** Coarse-grained evaluation: a 4-bit MPS is obtained from a 6-bit MPS by an average over the smallest (pink) spatial scale, both in x and in y . The averaging is implemented directly on the MPS through a simple contraction of the relevant sites with a constant single-site tensor (green ball). **d.** Pixel sampling: mesh cells (red points) are randomly chosen with probabilities proportional to the squared vorticity field at those points. The key tool are the marginals of the joint probability distributions over the binary representation of the cell positions. These allow one to sample the entire string bit by bit, conditioning each bit to the previously sampled one. The marginals can be efficiently obtained directly from the MPS. In the figure, a 2-bit marginal distribution is obtained through simple single-site contractions of two copies of 4-bit MPS and the gadget tensors in yellow. Remarkably, neither operation mode of the oracle requires field evaluations in the dense-vector representation (see Sec. III C).

encode the solutions of the INSE into MPSs. Indeed, even in the turbulent regime, the dynamics at a given scale is influenced only by the dynamics happening at the neighboring scales, and the interactions between well separated scales are suppressed, reflecting the well known energy cascade mechanism [3].

III. COMPLETE MPS FRAMEWORK FOR CFD

Here, we describe the proposed framework, summarized in Fig. 1. The first step of the algorithmic pipeline

(see Fig. 1a) is to initialize the velocity MPSs as constant vector fields, which characterize the flow far from the immersed body. The second step is to make such MPS fields compatible with the immersed object. In Sec. III A, we develop a systematic procedure to do this based on *approximate MPS masks* for the object (see Fig. 1b). The third step is to impose the incompressibility condition in Eq. (1b), according to the method outlined in Sec. III B. The fourth step closes the time evolution loop, from step two to four, with the explicit Euler time stepping. Finally, in step five, the resulting velocity field is recovered from its MPS encoding. We present two different

methods: *coarse-grained evaluation* (see Fig. 1c), and *pixel sampling* (see Fig. 1d). The details of both are explained in Sec. III C. In Sec. III D we present the complexity analysis of the different parts of the algorithm along with observed scaling of its runtime. To the best of our knowledge, this work constitutes the first report of a full MPS-based solver able to simulate fluid flows in non-trivial geometries. Moreover, we emphasize that, here, we focus explicitly on the 2D case for simplicity, but each and all of the components of the framework can be straightforwardly generalized to the 3D case.

A. Approximate MPS masks

When a rigid body is immersed in a fluid flow at a fixed position, the velocity vector must be null both inside the object and on its boundary, the latter due to the no-slip condition. This is a crucial requirement for any CFD framework to be useful in practice and, to the best of our knowledge, has not been previously addressed in the literature of quantum-inspired solvers. To incorporate this condition, we develop a theoretical and constructive recipe for *approximate MPS masks*. These are MPS-encoded fields that can approximate the indicator function of the object – i.e. the function evaluating to zero within the enclosure of the object and to one outside it – up to arbitrary, tunable precision. Once the approximate MPS mask is obtained, we enforce the nullification of the flow inside the object in a practical way by element-wise multiplication between the MPS mask itself and the MPS representing the field under consideration.

In order to build such an MPS, we begin by considering a scalar function $q(\mathbf{x})$ for $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{R}^D$, with the following properties: *i*) it vanishes on the boundary of the D -dimensional object in question, *ii*) it takes negative values in the interior of the object, and *iii*) it tends to infinity far from the boundary (a graphical illustration is given in Fig. 1b for the one-dimensional segment). For example, for a circular object of unit radius in $D = 2$, $q(x, y) = x^2 + y^2 - 1$ does the job. Using such boundary functions, we design the approximate mask

$$m(\mathbf{x}) := 1 - e^{-\alpha(q(\mathbf{x})+|q(\mathbf{x})|)}, \quad (3)$$

with $\alpha > 0$. By construction, $m(\mathbf{x})$ approximates the target indicator function increasingly better, in terms of l_2 -distance, for growing values of α . For more details on the choice of α see App. A. The next step is to obtain the MPS representation of $m(\mathbf{x})$. We remark that for elementary functions there are analytical ways to construct the associated MPSs [29, 30]. However, for complicated functions such as $m(\mathbf{x})$, we need to resort to numerical techniques. The specific numerical technique we use is the standard TT-cross approximation [31]. It builds the MPS approximation to $m(\mathbf{x})$, with controllable l_2 -distance, requiring only few function evaluations. We empirically observe that an l_2 -distance $\epsilon \sim 10^{-3}$, between the MPS mask and $m(\mathbf{x})$, is enough to produce

good quality masks up to 30 bits, where ϵ is evaluated via a Monte Carlo estimate. We note that a more naive approach would be to apply the TT-cross approximation to the indicator function itself, without even constructing $m(\mathbf{x})$. However, this procedure is observed to produce a poor quality MPS both qualitatively and quantitatively in terms of l_2 -distance, as explained in App. A.

B. Time evolution

In order to perform time evolution, we begin by discretizing the differential operators in Eqs. (1) using finite differences with an 8th order stencil [32]. We apply inlet and outlet open boundary conditions on the left and right edges of the domain to capture the fluid entering and exiting the domain accurately. To this aim, we modify the differential operators to satisfy [33]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{v}(t) &= \vec{v}_{in}, \quad \frac{\partial p(t)}{\partial n} = 0, \quad @ \text{ inlet}, \\ \frac{\partial v_i(t)}{\partial n} &= 0, \quad p(t) = p_0, \quad @ \text{ outlet}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Remarkably, the resulting matrices can be analytically mapped into their corresponding MPO representations with a low bond dimension [30, 34, 35].

As it is outlined in Fig. 1a, the very first step in order to simulate the dynamics consists of the initialization of the flow field. Once the flow is initialized, we loop over the three core stages of Fig. 1a (from the second to the fourth panel). The first stage involves the application of the MPS mask to the initial MPS velocity field via element-wise multiplication so that the no-slip condition on the object's boundary is satisfied. Once the mask is applied, the second stage consists of the projection of the MPS velocity field onto the divergence-free manifold defined by Eq. (1b). To do this, we solve a Poisson equation for pressure, which dominates the computational runtime of each time step. We tackle this core task with a DMRG-type algorithm, that solves the linear system associated with the Poisson equation [36]. In the next stage, we use the Euler explicit time stepping to evolve the velocity field according to the momentum Eq. (1a), without considering the pressure term. The resulting velocity field will not satisfy the no-slip and divergence-free conditions anymore, and we correct this during the first and second stages of the next iteration. This splitting of the time integration is known in CFD as the Chorin's projection method [37, 38]. The details of the time stepping procedure are presented in App. B, while in App. E we elaborate on its stability criteria.

C. MPS solution oracle

Our solver delivers the solution to Eqs. (1a) and (1b) directly in the MPS form. This gives the method a built-

in versatility in terms of how to access the solution. For grids of moderate size, one can map the obtained MPS back to the dense vector representation and so obtain the solution values at all the grid cells, i.e. the solution at full resolution. Nevertheless, the grid size grows exponentially in the number N of spatial scales supported by the MPS. This raises the question of how to handle the MPS solution when the corresponding grid is too large for a full-resolution evaluation. To this aim, we propose two main practical methods to efficiently extract the main features of the solution directly from the MPS: *coarse-grained evaluation* and *pixel sampling*. These two operation modes of our *MPS solution oracle* can additionally be combined with an extra auxiliary mode, *close-ups*.

For coarse-grained evaluation, one first averages small spatial scales out until the resulting grid is small (i.e., the minimum cell size is large) enough to allow for a full-resolution evaluation. This can be done in an extremely efficient manner on the MPSs: as sketched in Fig. 1c, one simply contracts the physical indices associated with the scales that one wishes to average out with single-site constant tensors (depicted in light-green in the figure). This operation returns an MPS with fewer spatial scales that encodes the desired coarse-grained version of the solution. The latter can then be mapped to the dense vector representation in full resolution. Clearly, the limitation of this approach is that the finest-scale details are lost, which can be essential for relevant scenarios. For instance, when simulating turbulent fluids at high Reynolds number, the minimum cell scale is typically chosen of the order of Kolmogorov scale ($\sim \text{Re}^{-3/4}$) [3]. For velocity and pressure fields in 3D, e.g., this means a mesh size $\sim \text{Re}^{9/4}$. In those cases, a convenient alternative is pixel sampling, which we explain next.

Pixel sampling is a technique to generate random grid points (x_i, y_j) chosen with probability $P(x_i, y_j) = |v_{i,j}|^2 / \|\mathbf{v}\|_2$, where $\|\mathbf{v}\|_2$ is the l_2 -norm of \mathbf{v} . Interestingly, this reproduces the measurement statistics on a quantum state that encodes \mathbf{v} in its amplitudes, hence being relevant also to future quantum solvers [39]. In addition, we note that related sampling methods have been used for training mesh-free neural-network solvers [40]. However, there the points are sampled uniformly, whereas here according to their relevance to the solution field. Our approach relies on standard efficient techniques for l_2 -norm sampling physical-index values from an MPS [7, 8]. The key ingredient is the marginals of $P(x_i, y_j)$, which can be computed by simple tensor contractions if \mathbf{v} is an MPS of low bond dimension [41, 42]. With the marginals, the conditional distribution for a bit given the previous ones can be straightforwardly obtained, allowing one to sample the entire bit string.

In Fig. 1d, we show an example of the type of tensor contractions used for this task. There, the two-bit marginal $P(i_1, i_2)$ is obtained by contracting two copies of \mathbf{v} with single-site tensors (depicted in light-yellow in the figure). Remarkably, all N marginals needed are calculated in this fashion without a single evaluation of \mathbf{v} at

Algorithmic task	Complexity	% runtime
Mask generation	$\mathcal{O}(N\chi^2)$	offline
Mask application	$\mathcal{O}(\chi^6)$	2.0
Divergence-free projection	$\mathcal{O}(N\chi^6)$	80.1
Euler time stepping	$\mathcal{O}(\chi^6)$	17.9
Coarse-grained evaluation	$\mathcal{O}(N_c\chi^3)$	offline
Pixel sampling	$\mathcal{O}(N_{ps}\chi^2)$	offline

TABLE I. **Worst-case time complexities and observed runtimes per task.** The first column shows the main sub-routines in our solver. Their corresponding asymptotic time-complexity upper bounds and numerically observed percentages of runtime are shown in the second and third columns, respectively. The theoretical estimates for the asymptotic bounds are determined according to N, χ - the number of bits and the bond dimension of the MPS encoding, N_c - the number of scales remaining after averaging out the finer scales during the coarse-grained evaluation, N_{ps} - the number of pixels sampled from the MPS. For the third column, we measure the runtime for performing time evolution of 100 time steps for the flow around a square cylinder, with a 15-bit MPS encoding. We present the percentages of runtime taken by the corresponding subroutines to identify the most expensive task. By offline, we mean that the step is performed only once, either before or after the time evolution stage.

any point (i, j) . Moreover, the technique applies to any MPS. For instance, one can obtain the MPS encoding the vorticity field from that of the velocity. Then, instead of evaluating it, one can directly sample the mesh points of highest vorticity, independently of the size of the mesh. In Sec. IV B, we show results for vorticity around a wing using coarse-grained evaluation and pixel sampling.

To end up with, we stress that both operation modes of the MPS solution oracle can also optionally be combined by *close-ups*, i.e. full-resolution evaluations within specifically chosen sub-domains (for instance, with a high accumulation of sampled pixels or where the coarse-grained evaluation suggests richer dynamics). A close-up is obtained straightforwardly by fixing the large-scale bits of $v_{i,j}$ so as to center it within the target sub-domain, with the number of fixed bits high enough to allow for a full-resolution evaluation on the remaining ones.

D. Complexity analysis

The asymptotic run-time of the proposed solver to find flow evolution for T time steps is $\mathcal{O}(TN\chi^6)$. In Table I, the scaling is broken down into the different steps of the algorithm, along with the observed percentage of the CPU time taken by each step. As already mentioned in Sec. III B, the projection step onto the divergence-free manifold of velocity fields, associated with the solution of a Poisson equation, is identified as the most intensive one. The time complexity of this sub-routine is estimated

FIG. 2. **Flow around a circular cylinder at various Reynolds numbers.** Each column shows one of the three paradigmatic phases of a laminar flow around a cylinder [43]. Top: streamlines, originating at the inlet (left side), are shown. The color code indicates the magnitude of velocity. The insets show the important features of the flow near the boundary of the object. Bottom: vorticity field $\vec{\omega} = \nabla \times \vec{v}$ is shown. The first column corresponds to $\text{Re} = 1.7$: in panel a, we observe that the streamlines do not detach from the edge of the cylinder. In turn, in panel d, no vorticity is observed behind the object. These are the signatures of a potential flow, where \vec{v} is given by the gradient of a scalar field. The second column corresponds to $\text{Re} = 25$. As seen in panel b, streamlines detach from the object's boundary. In turn, in panel e, a pair of counter-rotating vortices appears behind the object. These are the characteristics of a steady laminar flow. The third column corresponds to $\text{Re} = 125$. In this regime, the flow becomes unsteady and develops the well-known Kármán vortex street [25]. This can be observed in panels c and f, where clear oscillations in the streamlines and in the vortices behind the object are shown. A 15-bit MPS with $\chi = 30$ is used for all cases. In all of them, the simulated flow reproduces the expected behaviour.

as the combined cost of tensor contractions ($\mathcal{O}(N\chi^4)$) needed to determine the linear system of equations of size $4\chi^2 \times 4\chi^2$, and of the solution of the linear system. As determined in [36], we solve the linear system directly. Indeed, although it scales as $\mathcal{O}(\chi^6)$, the bond dimensions of the solution were small enough ($\chi \leq 45$) to allow the direct computation. This motivates our choice against an approximate iterative solution, whose favorable scaling $\mathcal{O}(\chi^3)$ is advantageous for larger bond dimensions. In order to reduce the cost of tensor contractions beyond $\mathcal{O}(N\chi^4)$, we use the **Random Greedy** optimizer of the `opt_einsum` package [44]. This finds the contraction order that is approximately minimal in terms of both space and time complexity [45]. Finding the exact optimal order of contraction is NP-hard [46, 47].

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Here, we present our solutions for flows around various immersed objects. In Sec. IV A, we benchmark our solver for circular and squared cylinders against known solutions. In Sec. IV B, we tackle more complex geometries: a collection of squared cylinders and a NACA airfoil. We provide more details on the way we choose the size of the time step and bond dimensions for the various geometries in App. E.

A. Benchmarking the MPS solver

We benchmark the MPS solver for the cases of flow around a circular cylinder and a squared cylinder, two of the most widely studied problems in fluid dynamics [25]. For the circular cylinder, we directly compare our solutions with experimental data [48–50], both qualitatively and quantitatively. We benchmark for different Re within the laminar regime, i.e. $\text{Re} \leq 150$. In all cases, we use a mesh with $N_x = 8$ horizontal scales and $N_y = 7$ vertical scales, encoded in a 15-bit MPS with $\chi = 30$ (for more details, see App. E2). For the qualitative comparison, in Fig. 2, we present the streamlines and vorticity of the MPS solutions at three different Reynolds numbers. We observe that the flow starts to develop vortices and oscillate with increasing Re . This behaviour is consistent with experimental observations across the three laminar sub-regimes [43]. In fact, in App. C, we compare two different observables, bubble length and Strouhal number, at six different Re , observing a reasonably good quantitative agreement (see Fig. A3 and related discussion in the appendix).

Next, we benchmark the MPS solver for flows around a squared cylinder for Reynolds numbers between 127 and 2230, i.e. where the laminar flow transitions towards turbulence. In this case, we compare the solutions of the MPS solver against those of **Ansys Fluent**. For $\text{Re} = 127, 630$, we use a mesh with $N_x = 8$ and $N_y = 7$ bits, whereas for $\text{Re} = 2230$, we use $N_x = 10$ and $N_y = 9$ bits. These are respectively encoded into 15- and 19-bit

FIG. 3. **Benchmark for the squared cylinder against Ansys Fluent commercial solver.** The top-left panel shows a schematic of the time evolution of bubble length. The upper plots in panels a, b and c correspond to the MPS solutions with 19, 15, and 15 bits, respectively, and $\chi = 30$. In turn, the lower plots in those panels correspond to solutions from Ansys Fluent, using the same mesh size. Panel a corresponds to $\text{Re} = 2230$ and $T = 6000$, i.e. an early stage of time evolution. This is often referred to as the developing phase of the fluid, where the difference in the numerical methods used is evident (see main text). Panel b corresponds to $\text{Re} = 630$ and $T = 11000$, when the highest bubble length is observed. Here, the flow is still developing, and the observed vortices differ in size. For $\text{Re} = 127$, in panel c, we present a snapshot at $T=19900$, during the unsteady and oscillating phase. Here, the flow reached the fully developed stage, and the top and bottom plots demonstrate similar features.

MPSs with $\chi = 30$. In Fig. 3, we plot the typical behaviour of the bubble length versus time T along with streamlines at three different Re and times. In panel a, for $\text{Re} = 2230$ and $T=6000$ (early stage of evolution), we observe that the vortices from the MPS solution (top) are smaller than ones from Ansys Fluent (bottom). We attribute this to the fact that Ansys Fluent uses a finite-volume method, whereas we use a finite-difference approach. In this initial, developing phase of the fluid, the difference between numerical methods is evident. Similarly, in panel b, we present the streamlines for $\text{Re} = 630$ at $T=11000$, the time step at which the peak bubble length is observed. This is still during the developing phase of the flow. Only after the oscillations form and stabilize, meaningful comparisons are possible. In fact, for $\text{Re} = 127$ and $T = 19900$, we reach this stable oscillatory phase of evolution. In panel c, we observe that the streamlines are in good agreement. In this case, the flow has reached the fully developed phase. To reach this phase for $\text{Re} = 630$ and 2230 , we are limited by the size of the time step (Δt) which influences the stability of the MPS solver, as explained in App. E 1.

Despite tackling simple geometries, we have reproduced varied and complex flow behaviours up to a Re of 2230. Additionally, we present a similar benchmark against Ansys Fluent for the flow around a collection of squared cylinders, in App. D.

B. Flow around complex geometries

Here, we venture into the simulations around geometries of higher complexity. First, we solve for the flow around a collection of four squared cylinders, arranged as shown in Fig. 4a. We simulate the flow at $\text{Re} = 141$ using a mesh of size $2^8 \times 2^7$, encoded into a 15-bit MPS with $\chi = 30$ (see App. E 2 for more details). The MPS mask is generated by extending the method of Sec. III A to the corresponding disjoint indicator function. We then integrate Eqs. (1) for $T = 10^4$ time steps. The various stages of time evolution are presented using streamlines in the top panels of Fig. 4. Additionally, in App. D, we compare our solutions against the ones from Ansys Fluent. We observe that both methods produce similar flow patterns during evolution.

Finally, we solve for the flow around a symmetric NACA 0040 airfoil [51], inclined at an angle of 22° and at $\text{Re} = 750$. We use this complex geometry to showcase the different operation modes of our solution oracle. We use $N_x = 10$ bits and $N_y = 9$ bits to discretize the domain, resulting in a mesh of size $2^{19} = 524288$. We encode the associated velocity and pressure fields into 19-bit MPSs with bond dimension $\chi = 45$ (see App. E 2 for more details). As mentioned in Sec. II B, since the virtual dimension of each matrix site is determined by the corresponding inter-scale correlations, the total number of parameters is reduced to 18800, well below the worst-case bound of $2N\chi^2$. This constitutes an impressive $27.9\times$ compression, for each spatial component of the velocity, as well as for the pressure. We perform time evolution for the velocity and the pressure MPSs for $T = 5000$ time steps. Then, from the resulting velocity MPSs, we directly obtain the corresponding vorticity MPS, defined as $\vec{\omega} = \nabla \times \vec{v}$, and take it as the solution oracle for the plots in the lower panels of Fig. 4. In Fig. 4d we display the vorticity field in full resolution and in Fig. 4e, we show the coarse-grained evaluation of vorticity after averaging over two scales in each direction. In Fig. 4f, we present 2500 pixels sampled from the squared vorticity field. We emphasize that the pixel sampling technique produces samples in the regions of highest vorticity, without ever evaluating the vorticity field itself.

The observed versatility to solve for flows involving complex geometries together with the built-in ability to access the solution directly from the MPS renders our framework potentially relevant to aero- and hydrodynamic design problems. For instance, pixel sampling is well-suited for Monte-Carlo estimations of objective functions that may be relevant to industrial optimizations.

FIG. 4. **Flow around complex geometries.** Top: different steps of the algorithmic pipeline (see Fig. 1a) are presented for the flow around a collection of four squares computed at $\text{Re} = 141$, using a 15-bit MPS with $\chi = 30$. **a.** Streamlines of the flow are shown after the mask has been applied to the uniform initialization of the velocity field. **b.** This panel corresponds to the streamlines after the projection of the velocity field onto the divergence-free manifold. **c.** Streamlines are presented after the iterating the time evolution for $T=10,000$ time steps, with $\Delta t = 10^{-3}$. Bottom: vorticity field around an inclined NACA 0040 airfoil is presented using the different evaluation modes (see Section III C). With $\text{Re} = 750$, a 19-bit MPS with $\chi = 45$ is used to encode the velocity fields. **d.** Here, we evaluate the full-resolution vorticity field from the vorticity MPS, that outputs the exponentially large dense representation. **e.** After averaging two scales in both x - and y -directions, we present the coarse-grained evaluation of the same vorticity MPS. This evaluation mode, in this case, reduces the memory requirement by 16 times. **f.** The pixel sampling mode is presented using a plot of 2500 pixels, sampled from the squared vorticity field. In the panel, the color represents the vorticity value queried directly at the sampled pixels from the vorticity MPS.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We have presented a complete, quantum-inspired framework for CFD based on matrix-product states (MPSs). Our solver supersedes previous works in that it incorporates immersed objects of diverse geometries, with non-trivial boundary conditions, and can retrieve the solution directly from the compressed MPS encoding, i.e. without ever passing through the expensive dense-vector representation. For a mesh of size 2^N , both the memory and the runtime scale linearly in N and polynomially in the bond dimension χ . The bond dimension grows with the complexity of the geometry in question. Nevertheless, we observe our toolbox to handle highly non-trivial geometries using remarkably low bond dimensions and number of parameters. For instance, the most challenging case we consider is a wing airfoil for a mesh of $2^{19} = 524288$ pixels with open boundary conditions. Our machinery accurately captures the corresponding flows with MPSs of $N = 19$ bits, $\chi = 45$, and a total of 18800 parameters. This constitutes an impressive $27.9\times$ compression, for each spatial component of the velocity, for the pressure, and also for the vorticity.

The core technical ingredient to enable such high efficiencies is the approximate MPS masks that we have introduced. These make it possible to accurately describe complex immersed objects using moderate χ 's. In fact, we have provided a versatile mask generation recipe ex-

ploiting standard tensor-network tools such as the TT-cross algorithm. Another key contribution is the alternative methods we have proposed to query the solution field directly from its MPS: coarse-grained evaluation and pixel sampling. In particular, pixel sampling explores random mesh points distributed according to the square of a chosen property, such as for instance vorticity or pressure (and, through an equation of state, also temperature). This mimics the measurement statistics of a quantum state encoding the property in its amplitudes, hence being relevant also to future quantum solvers [39]. Remarkably, it does so by efficiently computing marginals of the target distribution via local tensor contractions directly on the MPS, without evaluating the property itself at a single mesh point. Pixel sampling is ideal for Monte-Carlo simulations, relevant to optimizations via stochastic gradient descent, e.g. This can be interesting to aero- or hydro-dynamic design problems as well as to training neural-network models.

Our work also offers several directions for future research. In particular, the extension to the 3D case will allow one to probe our framework in truly turbulent regimes. We stress that further optimization of our tensor-network architecture is possible and might play a crucial role for that, as well as extensions to non-uniform meshes. Another interesting possibility is the exploration of tensor-network approaches in other natural function bases for turbulent phenomena, such as Fourier [52] or

wavelets [53]. In turn, an interesting opportunity is the application of our framework to other partial differential equations. This may be combined with potential extensions to finite elements or finite volumes, which can in principle also be translated to tensor networks [24]. Moreover, our method may even be relevant to mesh-free solvers too. For instance, pixel sampling on small meshes could be applied to speed-up the training in mesh-free neural-network schemes [40]. Finally, a further possibility could be to combine our framework with quantum

algorithms, in view of hybrid solvers based on classical tensor-network techniques and quantum sub-routines. For example, our computational bottleneck is the Poisson equation at each time step, and future quantum linear solvers may offer significant speed-ups for that [39].

All in all, our findings open a playground with potential to build radically more efficient solvers of real-life fluid dynamics problems as well as other high-dimensional partial differential equation systems, with far-reaching research and technology implications.

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Supplementary Information

Appendix A: Mask generation

In this appendix, we provide details about the generation of approximate MPS masks outlined in Sec. III A.

1. Smooth analytical approximation for the indicator function

We begin by analyzing how well the mask function $m(\mathbf{x})$, introduced in Eq. (3), approximates the indicator function $\theta(\mathbf{x})$ of a given object. We refer to Fig. 1b for a schematic illustration.

Statement 1: The l_2 -distance d_2 between the indicator function $\theta(\mathbf{x})$ and its smooth approximation $m(\mathbf{x})$, for arbitrary objects, scales with α as $d_2(\theta(\mathbf{x}), m(\mathbf{x})) \sim 1/\sqrt{\alpha}$.

Proof: For the 1D case of a segment, $q(x) = x^2 - L_0^2$, where $2L_0$ is the segment length. Then, the analytical squared l_2 -distance between $\theta(x)$ and $m(x)$ evaluates to

$$\begin{aligned} [d_2(\theta(x), m(x))]^2 &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (\theta(x) - m(x))^2 dx \\ &= 2 \int_{L_0}^{+\infty} e^{-2\alpha(q(x)+|q(x)|)} dx \\ &= 2 e^{4\alpha L_0^2} \int_{L_0}^{+\infty} e^{-4\alpha x^2} dx \\ &= e^{4\alpha L_0^2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4\alpha}} \operatorname{erfc}(\sqrt{4\alpha L_0^2}) \\ &\xrightarrow{a \gg 1} \frac{1}{4\alpha L_0}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Using similar arguments for the D -dimensional cube of side length L_0 , the l_2 -distance behaves as $d_2 \sim \sqrt{L_0^{D-2}/\alpha}$. This argument can be extended to arbitrary objects, for which the l_2 -distance in general is given by $C\alpha^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where C is independent of α . We observe that, for every geometry considered in this work, $\alpha = 10^3$ is sufficient to guarantee a good enough approximation.

2. MPS approximation using TT-cross

We first explain the generation of the MPSs using the TT-cross algorithm [31]. Then, we present a comparison of MPS masks generated from the indicator function $\theta(\mathbf{x})$ and its smooth approximation $m(\mathbf{x})$.

Each MPS mask is built by applying the TT-cross algorithm to its corresponding mask function. Given a discretized function over N bits, the TT-cross algorithm builds the associated MPS approximation by querying (15000 times in our case) the function itself. The samples are drawn according to a cross-sketching scheme [31],

but without the need to effectively evaluate the dense, exponential-in- N , vector representation. Then, with the use of acquired samples, TT-cross builds a sequence of CUR decompositions [54, 55].

Fig. A1 qualitatively demonstrates that the MPS approximation produced by TT-cross is much better when a smoother function like $m(\mathbf{x})$ is given as input. In fact, we observe artifacts and random deviations in masks generated from indicator function by making the plot of 22 bit MPS in full resolution in the first and second columns of the Fig A1.b. We proceed our analysis by extending the domain to 30 bits, where we find even worse approximations when building the MPS mask directly from $\theta(\mathbf{x})$. Indeed, in the 3rd and 4th columns of Fig. A1, we plot the two MPS masks arising from the two different application of the TT-cross algorithm for $N_x = 15$, $N_y = 15$ bits domain. In order to plot them, we employed the two native operational modes, introduced in Sec. III C, to recover the vector representation from its MPS one when the number of bits is too high to allow a direct evaluation.

The quality of the MPS mask is crucial for our fluid simulations, as it explained in Sec. IIIB. Indeed, the mask needs to be applied at each time step in the iterative solver and any artifact would act as an external source term on the dynamics, leading to different physical solutions.

3. Bond dimension vs number of bits

In this section, we show the scaling of the bond dimension when the number of bits is increased. In particular, we argue that an MPS mask with a bond dimension $\chi \leq 30$ is sufficient to capture, i.e. to approximate with a good enough accuracy, the target function $m(\mathbf{x})$. For the sake of completeness, we conduct the analysis also on MPSs obtained directly from $\theta(\mathbf{x})$, for which we find much worse accuracy as expected. In particular, in Fig. A2, we show the l_2 -distance between the MPS approximation and its target function, which is either $\theta(\mathbf{x})$ or $m(\mathbf{x})$. Much better approximations are obtained when using $m(\mathbf{x})$, confirming the results from the previous section. Moreover, when considering $m(\mathbf{x})$, the bond dimension required to achieve a good accuracy does not scale with the number of bits, and we find that $\chi = 30$ is sufficient for our purposes.

FIG. A1. **Comparison between MPS masks obtained via the indicator function and its smooth approximation.** The top row (a) depicts MPS masks obtained via $m(\mathbf{x})$, while the bottom one (b) corresponds to the masks generated via $\theta(\mathbf{x})$. The first column displays $N_x = 11$, $N_y = 11$ bit MPS in full resolution, the second one demonstrates the difference between the first column mask and the indicator function $\theta(\mathbf{x})$. In the last two columns, we present an instance of 30 bit MPS mask. In 3rd column, we average 4 scales in each direction using coarse-grained evaluation. In the final column, we present 1.2×10^5 pixels sampled from the MPS mask. The bond dimension is taken to be $\chi = 30$ for all MPSs presented in the figure. By comparing (a) and (b) rows, we see that MPS masks obtained from $m(\mathbf{x})$ are more accurate than the ones obtained directly from $\theta(\mathbf{x})$, which show random deviations from the values of the target function.

FIG. A2. **Monte Carlo estimates of l_2 -distance between the MPS masks and their target functions for increasing number of bits and different bond dimensions.** The Figure shows that, when using $m(\mathbf{x})$ to build the MPS mask, a very good accuracy can be reached even with a constant bond dimension of $\chi = 30$, independently of the number of bits used. The distance is computed sampling the MPS mask 30000 times and normalizing the l_2 -distance over the number of samples. Then, since TT-cross is a stochastic process, we run it 30 times and average the results to get a single point in the plot, with its associated standard deviation shown as shaded areas. The TT-cross is always run with a limit of $\chi = 100$ in the bond dimension, and the truncation is performed on top of the obtained mask at the end of the process.

Appendix B: Time evolution

Here, we present the details of the time evolution and numerical integration used in the proposed framework. The main objective here is to evolve velocity fields within the divergence-free manifold. To achieve this, we use the Chorin's projection method [37, 38] together with finite-difference scheme.

We begin with the discretization of time in the INSE stated in Sec. II A. We choose the explicit Euler time-stepping scheme, resulting in the following:

$$\frac{\vec{v}_{t+\Delta t} - \vec{v}_t}{\Delta t} + (\vec{v}_t \cdot \nabla) \vec{v}_t = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p_{t+\Delta t} + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v}_t + \vec{f}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

along with the divergence-free condition:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v}_{t+\Delta t} = 0. \quad (\text{B2})$$

Next, we ignore the pressure term in Eq. (B1) to produce an intermediate velocity field given by

$$\vec{v}_{t+\Delta t}^* = \vec{v}_t + (-(\vec{v}_t \cdot \nabla) \vec{v}_t + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v}_t + \vec{f}) \times \Delta t. \quad (\text{B3})$$

However, Eq. (B3) does not satisfy the divergence-free condition. We then use the Helmholtz decomposition of the intermediate velocity field $\vec{v}_{t+\Delta t}^*$. This results in two orthogonal components, a solenoidal and an irrotational vector field. By definition, the solenoidal field has zero divergence at all points, which is indeed our objective.

Next, instead of finding the solenoidal component directly, we determine the irrotational component of the intermediate velocity. As stated in the Chorin's projection

method [37], this reduces to solving the Poisson equation for the pressure field:

$$\nabla^2 p_{t+\Delta t} = \frac{\rho}{\Delta t} \nabla \cdot \vec{v}_{t+\Delta t}^*. \quad (\text{B4})$$

By subtracting the gradient of the pressure field, we find the solenoidal component of the velocity field, which completes the time evolution for one time step:

$$\vec{v}_{t+\Delta t} = \vec{v}_{t+\Delta t}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho} \nabla p_{t+\Delta t}. \quad (\text{B5})$$

Using this as the starting point, we integrate again using the above described procedure. We also note that, after encoding the vector fields into corresponding MPSs, we enforce the no-slip boundary condition by applying the *approximate MPS masks* during each time step of the evolution.

Appendix C: Experimental benchmark for the circular cylinder

Here, we benchmark the flow around the circular cylinder against experimental evidence [48–50]. In Fig. A3, we plot the bubble length and the Strouhal number for different Re . We see that the simulations reproduce the experimental trends. However, we also observe that the MPS solver does not exactly match the experimental data. One of the potential reasons for this mismatch could be the low resolution at the boundary of the cylinder. With the current mesh size ($2^8 \times 2^7$), the discretized object does not have a smooth circular boundary.

FIG. A3. **Experimental benchmark for the flow around the circular cylinder.** In panel a, we present the bubble length (l_b) versus Re . The bubble length is defined as the region behind the immersed object where a back flow in the x -direction is observed, i.e. $v_x < 0$. The data plotted corresponds to the largest bubble length observed during the time evolution. In panel b, we plot the Strouhal number against Re . Strouhal number, defined as $St = \frac{fL}{U}$, is a dimensionless parameter which determines the oscillations of the flow. Here, f is the frequency of the average velocity magnitude behind the object, and L, U are the characteristic length and velocity defined in the Sec. II A.

Appendix D: Comparison for a collection of squares against Ansys Fluent

In this appendix, we compare the flow around a collection of squares, described in Sec. IV B, against the solutions from Ansys Fluent. We use $N_x = 8$ and $N_y = 7$ bits for the mesh and simulate the flow at $Re=141$ for $T=10,000$ time steps. The velocity components were encoded in 15-bit MPSs of $\chi = 30$. In Fig. A4, we present the velocity magnitude at full resolution for three intermediate time steps. We notice that the broader features of the flow are in good agreement.

FIG. A4. **Benchmark of MPS solver against Ansys Fluent for the flow around a collection of squared cylinders.** We present the velocity magnitude at three intermediate time steps. In the left column, we present the solutions obtained from the MPS solver, using a mesh size of $2^8 \times 2^7$ at $Re = 141$. In the right panels, we show the corresponding solutions from Ansys Fluent, using the same mesh size.

Appendix E: Numerical Solver

Along with specifying the domain, mesh size, and boundary conditions, we also need to choose the size of the time step (Δt) which affects the stability of the time integration, and the bond dimension (χ) of the MPS encoding which controls both the accuracy and compression achieved during the simulation. Here we explain the criteria for the choice of both these parameters.

1. Stability of the algorithm

For a stable time evolution, we have to satisfy the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition [56]. It states that for $(\frac{U\Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq 1)$, where U is the characteristic velocity, the information about the flow travels slower than

the flow itself, ensuring stable numerical integration. We emphasize that this is only a necessary condition, but not sufficient for the stability of the algorithm. However, using this relationship between the temporal resolution (Δt) and spatial resolution (Δx), we can estimate an upper bound on the size of the time step.

2. Truncation of the bond dimension

First, we explain the truncation of singular values for determining the virtual dimensions of the MPS encoding. During the time evolution, at several stages, the inter-scale correlations of the velocity field change. The Schmidt coefficients, or singular values, at each virtual dimension, determine the corresponding amount of inter-scale correlations. To achieve maximum compression, we throw away the smallest singular values such that the l_2 -norm of the discarded singular values is below a pre-defined threshold ε . For all the cases in this work, we choose $\varepsilon = 10^{-16}$.

As defined in Sec. II B, the bond dimension is defined as the maximum of all the virtual dimensions of an MPS. By fixing the maximum bond dimension allowed, we affect the power of compression, the runtime as well as the accuracy of the MPS solver. For instance, in the case of flow around a cylinder, we observe that fixing the maximum bond dimension $\chi = 30$, the difference in divergence when compared with the MPS without fixing χ is insignificant. In Fig. A5, we present the behaviour of divergence versus time for both cases and compare a snapshot of the velocity field. We note that this maximum bond dimension allowed differs from case and case and is reported as and when needed throughout the text.

FIG. A5. **Comparison of solutions with fixed and unfixed bond dimension χ .** In panels a and b, we plot the velocity magnitude of the solutions obtained with a fixed bond dimension of $\chi = 30$ and unfixed χ , respectively. In panel c, we show the behaviour of divergence for both cases against time. Panel d corresponds to the absolute difference between the velocity fields of panel a and b.